

Improving Facility Operations: A Quantitative Evaluation of MTBF, MTTR, and SLA Targets

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Abstract

This study evaluated facility operations services by means of exploring key metrics like Mean Time to Repair (MTTR), Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF), Service Level Agreement (SLA) targets, Reliability ($R(t)$) and Failure Rate (λ). The analysis was carried out in three regions namely Eastern region, Northern region, and Western region by x-raying 10 months of data collected from operational records, incident logs, and SLA compliance results from a facilities maintenance company in Nigeria. The Western region was faced with the highest number of incidents, peaking at 933 in the month of April, while that of the Eastern region recorded 371 incidents in the month of May, and the Northern region had 166 incidents in the month of August all in year 2024. MTBF was used to measure failure frequency, while the MTTR provided insights into incident resolution times. In the Western region, the MTTR averaged 2.5 hours in the month of April, resulting to operational inefficiencies. The facility efficiency was measured against a 95% SLA target and the performance shows a drop to about 76% in the month of March but there was efforts along the line that shows recovery to 100% by the month of September and October 2024. The reliability analysis also showed that the high incident rates negatively impacted operational continuity. The outcome of this study emphasizes the significance of constantly monitoring the MTBF, the MTTR, and the SLA compliance to improve operational efficiency. The findings also highlight the Western region's operational challenges and the need for focused on improvements in the maintenance and repair processes method of pattern to attain steady 99-100% efficiency across all regions.

Keywords: *Mean Time to Repair (MTTR), Service level Agreement (SLA), Mean Time between Failures (MTBF), Failure rate, Reliability, Facility operations, Facilities.*

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Introduction

Facility operations is the coordination and management of various facilities services, systems, and processes that ensure the functionality, comfort, safety, and efficiency of buildings or infrastructure or equipment. These operations are crucial in supporting the core functions of any organisation by ensuring

that its physical spaces are efficiently and effectively optimised for usage (Wetzel & Thabet, 2015). In a fast developing business atmosphere, where efficiency and cost control are paramount, effective facility management becomes a key differentiator for both business continuity and growth (Amos et al., 2020). Facilities range from office buildings, data centers, and manufacturing plants to hospitals, schools, and retail spaces. The scope of facility operations covers numerous areas such as energy management, HVAC (Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning) systems, lighting, plumbing, and security systems (Al Shalabi, 2016). Quantitatively, this study seeks to evaluate the present state of facility operational efficiency, by examining the historical operational performance data that was collected to determine the trends in efficiency over the period of 10 months' period, thereafter identify times of high and low efficiency, by stating the major reasons that was responsible for these deviations from agreed SLA. Then, compare actual operational performance against established SLA benchmarks to validate compliance and reliability within the work place.

Literature Review

The ultimate aim of this research work is to assess and enhance facility operational efficiency by analysing maintenance and reliability measuring tools such as Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF), Mean Time to Repair (MTTR), and Service Level Agreement (SLA) compliance. Operational efficiency in facility management is critical to ensuring that a facility's systems, services, and infrastructure function effortlessly and with cost effectiveness too (Kavinya, 2019). With reference to the perspective of facility operations, efficiency means increasing the performance of assets, reducing resource depletion, and decreasing downtime caused by equipment failures or the equipment repairs. Efficient operations transform to sustained productivity, reduced operational spending, and enhanced user satisfaction, making it a vital focus area for any organization poised for progress and profit maximization (Parida & Kumar, 2009).

Key Performance Metrics in Facility Operations

a. Mean Time between Failures (MTBF)

Mean Time between Failures (MTBF) refers to performance metric or process used to measure the reliability system or equipment (Duenckel et al, 2017). This is the average time that passes between one failures occurred and when the next failure happened in between normal operation. Below is the MTBF formula to calculate it:

$$MTBF = \frac{\text{Total Operational Time}}{\text{Number of Failures}} \quad (1)$$

For instance, can that an equipment runs for a 1,000 hour and during the process, it experienced 10 failures, the MTBF can be calculated as:

$$MTBF = \frac{1000}{10} = 100 \text{ Hours}$$

What this means is that, for every 100 hours the systems or of piece of equipment will likely tend to experience a failure. MTBF is a critical metric that is used in facility operations because it provides an indication of how reliable systems or piece of equipment will be over time. A higher MTBF denotes that the piece of equipment or system will operates for longer periods without failing or running out, which

is a crucial consideration for ensuring continuous and uninterrupted services within a facility or work place (Żyluk et al., 2023).

b. Mean Time to Repair (MTTR)

Mean Time to Repair (MTTR) is a performance metric that is used when measuring the average time that will be taken to repair a system or piece of equipment after a failure has occurred. It reveals how fast a facility can return to normal operation after a systems breakdown. The goal is to minimise MTTR to ensure that downtime is as short as possible (Selvik & Ford, 2017).

See MTTR calculated as:

$$MTTR = \frac{\text{Total Downtime for Repairs}}{\text{Number of Repairs}} \quad (2)$$

For example, if equipment fails five times in a month, and if the total time spent on repairs is 50 hours, the MTTR would be:

$$MTTR = \frac{50 \text{ Hours}}{5} = 10 \text{ hours}$$

MTTR is one of the critical apparatus used by facilities data analyst because it provides facility managers with the required insight into the efficiency and also shed more light in the effectiveness of the maintenance processes (Okirie, 2024). Whenever a lower MTTR is gotten, it means that repairs were completed in a faster manner, thereby reducing the impact of interruption on facility operations (Berrabah et al., 2022). It also shows how speedily a maintenance technician or technical team can respond to issues as they occur and resolve equipment or systems failures timeously, making it one of the important pointer of a facility's alertness in managing unexpected failure events. The determination and understanding of MTTR definitely helps facility managers to optimize maintenance workflows, recognize bottlenecks, and allocate resources more effectively to reduce downtimes (Narayan, 2004). Lower MTTR also ensures better allocation of maintenance staff, tools, and spare parts, in ensuring that the right resources are in place to address failures as quickly as possible and it leads to improved system availability and uptime, thereby enabling facilities to meet or exceed the stated Service Level Agreement (SLA) targets and maintaining operational reliability (Daniewski et al., 2018).

c. Service Level Agreement (SLA)

A Service Level Agreement (SLA) is a formal contract between a service provider and a client that defines the level of service expected. In the context of facility operations, SLAs typically outline performance targets related to operational uptime, response times, and the resolution of issues within specified timeframes. For facilities management, SLAs are essential for ensuring that buildings, equipment, and services operate at optimal levels, minimising downtime and disruptions (Bouillet et al., 2002).

In facility management, SLA targets might include specific metrics such as:

i. Operational Efficiency: A percentage target depends on the agreement between the client and the service provider, for the purpose of this study, we are using 95% which reflects the proportion of time that facility systems or assets must be fully operational.

ii. Incident Response Time: A maximum allowable time to respond to issues or service requests, typically outlined in hours or minutes.

iii. Resolution Time: The agreed timeframe to resolve incidents, such as breakdowns or maintenance requests.

Achieving these SLA targets ensures that facilities operate smoothly, service disruptions are minimized, and operational goals are met in line with business requirements.

iv. Compliance Rate Calculation

SLA compliance rates can be expressed as a percentage, showing the ratio of successfully achieved targets compared to total expected targets (Sommers et al., 2007).

For example, if 95 incidents occurred and 90 were resolved within the SLA limits, the compliance rate would be:

$$SLA \text{ Compliance Rate} = \frac{90}{95} \times 100 = 94.7\%$$

Compliance rates above **95%** typically indicate strong adherence to SLA targets, whereas lower rates suggest areas needing improvement.

v. Penalties for Non-Compliance

Many SLAs include penalty clauses for failure to meet the agreed targets (Ayd, 2017). For example, if a facility consistently misses its response or resolution times, financial penalties or service credits might be enforced, further emphasizing the importance of meeting SLA targets. Measuring SLA compliance ensures that facility operations are functioning as expected, downtime is minimized, and the organization can meet its operational goals. Achieving and maintaining high compliance rates reinforces the reliability of facility services and the efficiency of the management team (Følstad & Helvik, 2016).

Methodology

The methodology for evaluating facility operational efficiency, incident trends, and service level compliance involves systematically collecting, analysing, and interpreting data gathered from various sources in facility management in a telecommunications environment. This study leverages Microsoft Excel as a primary tool for organising, analysing, and visualising the data. The process involves several key stages, including data collection, data cleaning, data processing, and analysis.

Data Collection and Data Sources

Data for this study was collected from the following key sources:

- i. Incident Reports:** Logs of incidents failures or service requests were collected from the facility's incident management system as shown in Table 3.1. These reports include information on the date of occurrence, the region affected, type of failure, and time taken to resolve the issue.
- ii. Operational Performance Logs:** Data on facility performance, including uptime and downtime, was sourced from facility management software or operational logs.
- iii. SLA Compliance Records:** Service Level Agreement (SLA) compliance data was derived from performance reports that measure how well the facility's operations met the predetermined SLA targets of 95% efficiency.

Data Entry in Excel

The data collected from the above sources were input into an Excel spreadsheet using structured tables.

Incident Number	State	Current Status	Week	Month	TAT	Ageing	Region	Created	Resolved	Subcategory	Priority	Resolve time
INCS136966	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	1	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 13:36:02	2024-09-13 13:36:13	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	157
INCS136957	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	1	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 13:33:07	2024-09-13 13:33:18	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	91
INCS136091	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	2	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 11:08:24	2024-09-13 11:08:39	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	158
INCS136082	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	1	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 11:05:23	2024-09-13 11:05:34	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	57
INCS136067	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	3	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 11:04:07	2024-09-13 11:04:20	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	68
INCS136056	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	1	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 11:02:46	2024-09-13 11:02:56	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	75
INCS136046	Resolved	Closed	Week 37	Sep	2	Below 5 days	East	2024-09-13 11:01:04	2024-09-13 11:01:20	Facilities Maintenance	4 - Low	68

Figure 1. Collected Data Incident Log

- i. Incident Data:** Includes columns for Date, Region (East, North, West), Number of Incidents, Resolution Time, and Repair Time.
- ii. Operational Efficiency Data:** This table includes Date (Week/Month), Downtime, Uptime, Efficiency (% uptime), and Target SLA.
- iii. SLA Compliance Data:** Captures Date, SLA Target at 95%, Actual Performance (%), and Deviation.

Data Processing and Cleaning

i. Data Cleaning

Once the data was input into Excel, the following steps were taken to clean the data:

- 1. Handling Missing Data:** Missing entries were filled using the average imputation method, where possible, or left as blanks if they were deemed non-essential.
- 2. Standardization of Units:** Time entries (such as repair times and downtime) were converted to a standard unit (hours) to ensure consistency across all datasets.
- 3. Duplicate Data Removal:** Duplicate entries (particularly in the incident data) were identified and removed to prevent skewed results.

ii. Data Structuring

The cleaned data was structured into appropriate formats for analysis. Pivot tables were created to summarize the data, specifically focusing on regional trends, weekly/monthly performance, and SLA compliance.

Data Analysis

i. Incident Trends Analysis

Using Excel's built in charting tools, the incident data was visualised through line graphs and bar charts to show the trend of incidents per region over time. Key insights, such as peak failure periods or regions with the highest number of incidents in West region in April with 933 incidents were highlighted.

Formulas used in Excel:

$Total\ Incident\ per\ region = sumif(Region, Region, [Incident])$

$Average\ Incidents = Avarage ([Incident])$

Operational Efficiency Analysis

The operational performance data was analyzed to calculate key metrics, including:

i. Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF): This was calculated using the formula:

$$MTBF = \frac{Total\ Operational\ Time}{Number\ of\ Failures} \quad (1)$$

Where total operational time is derived from uptime logs, and number of failures is from incident data.

ii. Mean Time to Repair (MTTR): MTTR was calculated for each region and over time using:

$$MTTR = \frac{Total\ Repair\ Time}{Number\ of\ Repairs} \quad (2)$$

Where repair time is the time taken to resolve an incident, as logged in the incident data.

iii. Efficiency (%): The facility efficiency was calculated based on the percentage of uptime using:

$$Efficiency = \left(\frac{Uptime}{(Uptime + Downtime)} \right) \times 100 \quad (3)$$

The results were visualized in line graphs representing weekly and monthly facility operational efficiency against the SLA target at 95%. Key performance drops, such as the efficiency falling to 76% in March, were highlighted for analysis.

SLA Compliance Analysis

Excel was used to calculate the deviation between the facility's actual performance and the SLA targets using the formula:

$$Deviation = Actual\ Performance - SLA\ Target \quad (4)$$

This allowed us to track when the facility was out of compliance that is, when efficiency below 95% and understand the recovery periods like reaching 100% in September.

Visualization and Reporting

Using Excel's data visualization tools, the key findings were illustrated in the following graphs in Figure 2:

- i. **Trend of Incidents Received from Regions per Month:** A line graph plotting incidents by region to identify trends.
- ii. **Facility Operational Efficiency- Weekly/Monthly:** Line graphs comparing actual efficiency to the SLA targets.
- iii. **Incident and Repair Statistics:** Bar charts highlighting the frequency of incidents and the average repair time per region.

Figure 2. Visualization and Reporting Dashboard

Results and Discussion

Service Level Agreement (SLA)

This is a formal contract that outlines the specific level of service expected from a provider. In this case, the SLA require the service provider to resolve 95% of incidents within a given time frame (weekly, based on the image). If the service provider fails to meet this target, penalties or compensation may apply.

The gauge chart displaying in Figure 3 shows the weekly incident resolution rate, which is part of a Service Level Agreement (SLA) metric. SLAs define the expected level of service between a service provider and a client, with specific measurable targets.

95% Target: According to the gauge below Figure 3, the resolution rate is just below 100%, indicated by a reading of 99%. The SLA target of 95% means the service provider have ensured that at least 95% of incidents are resolved within the agreed-upon time.

Current Performance (99%): The chart shows the performance for the week is at 99%, which exceeds the SLA target of 95%. This means the service provider is surpassing the agreed performance level, indicating excellent service delivery for that week.

Figure 3. The Incident Rating Gauge

Incident Resolution Performance

The range between 95-100% is in the dark green section of the gauge, indicating excellent service performance. Since the pointer is almost at the maximum, this means that the service provider is resolving nearly all incidents, likely exceeding the agreed SLA performance requirements. The gauge reflects the weekly incident resolution rate, showing an exceptionally high rate of 99%. If the SLA requires 95% of incidents to be resolved, which is common and also depends on the agreement between both parties, the current performance surpasses this target. This indicates strong service delivery for the period.

Red (0-20%): Indicates poor incident resolution performance.

Yellow (30-60%): Represents average or moderate performance.

Light Green (75-90%): Represents good performance.

Dark Green (95-100%): Represents excellent performance, surpassing most SLA targets.

In the context of Service Level Agreements (SLA), a typical target could be to resolve 95% of incidents within a specific time frame (in this case, weekly). The Figure 4 indicates that the current incident resolution rate is 99%, which falls in the dark green "excellent" range. The service provider has performed above the SLA target, ensuring nearly all incidents were resolved within the expected time. The current performance of 99% incident resolution exceeds a typical SLA target of 95%, indicating that the service provider is delivering exceptional service for the week.

Weekly Facility Operational Efficiency

The weekly Facility Operational Efficiency as shown in Figure 4, is comparing the facility's operational efficiency (in blue) to the SLA target in orange, which is fixed at 95%. The blue line tracks weekly efficiency, which fluctuates between 86% and 100%. Weeks where the efficiency exceeds the 95% SLA target (orange line) indicate better reliability and fewer failures. Conversely, when efficiency dips below 95%, it suggests an increase in failure rates or longer repair times. Weeks 32 (86%) and 31 (94%) show significant drops in efficiency, indicating either frequent failures (low MTBF) or slow repair times (high MTTR). Meanwhile, Weeks 29, 38, and 39, with 100% efficiency, represent periods of high reliability, no or rare failures, and quick recovery times.

To explain this in relation to Mean Time between Failures (MTBF), Mean Time to Repair (MTTR), Failure Rate, and Reliability, these key performance metrics are explained below.

Figure 4. Weekly Facility Operational Efficiency Graph

i. Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF):

MTBF represents the average time between system failures during operation. The spikes in operational efficiency as shown in Figure 4 at Week 29 attained 100% and Weeks 38 to 39 also attained 100%, which suggest periods with minimal or no system failures, meaning the MTBF during these weeks would be high. However, a sharp dip at Week 32 at 86% show a lower MTBF, suggesting more frequent failures during that period. MTBF is higher in weeks with 99-100% efficiency, lower in weeks with efficiency below 95%.

ii. Mean Time to Repair (MTTR):

MTTR is the average time taken to repair the system and bring it back to operational status after failure. Weeks with lower efficiency values as shown in Figure 4 such as Week 32 (86%), likely have higher MTTRs because more time was needed to repair and restore the system. Higher efficiency weeks from Weeks 33 to indicate faster recovery from failures, leading to lower MTTRs. MTTR is higher in weeks where efficiency dropped below 95%, indicating longer repair times.

iii. Failure Rate (λ):

The Failure Rate is the frequency of failures over a period of time and is inversely related to MTBF.

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{MTBF} \tag{5}$$

Weeks with lower operational efficiency in Figure 4 like Week 32 at 86% would correspond to a higher failure rate, indicating the system failed more often. Conversely, weeks with 100% efficiency like Week 29 and Weeks 38 to 39 would have low or zero failure rates, meaning few or no system failures. Failure rate is inversely related to MTBF, meaning higher during weeks with low efficiency like Week 32.

iv. Reliability (R):

Reliability measures the probability that a system will perform without failure for a specified time period, and is related to MTBF as follows:

$$R(t) = e^{-\lambda t} \tag{6}$$

Since reliability depends on the failure rate (λ), weeks with higher efficiency have higher reliability. For example, in Week 29, at 100% efficiency, the system is highly reliable with low failure rates. On the other hand, with Week 32 at 86% efficiency, this suggests lower reliability due to increased failure frequency. Reliability is strongest when the system meets or exceeds the SLA target of 95%, as seen in Weeks 33-40.

Monthly Facility Operational Efficiency

The Monthly facility performance is strong as shown in Figure 5 with only a few weeks falling below the SLA target of 95%, reflecting solid reliability and generally low failure rates. The Monthly Facility Operational Efficiency report, comparing the facility's operational efficiency in blue to the Service Level Agreement (SLA) target in orange, as shown in Figure 5 which is set at 95%. The chart tracks efficiency over the months from January to October, with efficiency percentages listed for each month.

Referring to efficiency (Blue Line) on Figure 5, the month of January and February start with a perfect 100% efficiency, meaning no failures or quick recovery after failures. The month of March sees a sharp drop to 76%, suggesting frequent failures or longer repair times, which lowers the facility's operational efficiency well below the SLA target. April to July shows a gradual recovery from 81% to 95%, improving the system's reliability and possibly lowering the failure rates or repair times. August (95%) aligns with the SLA target, indicating the facility is just meeting its performance agreement. September (99%) and October (100%) demonstrate excellent performance, with efficiency exceeding the SLA target, indicating near-optimal operational reliability and minimal downtime.

Figure 5. Monthly Facility Operational Efficiency Graph

Explanation Using Reliability Metrics

i. Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF):

MTBF is higher in months like January, February, September, and October (99%-100% efficiency), indicating long periods between failures. The sharp dip in March (76%) suggests a lower MTBF, meaning more frequent failures occurred in this month.

ii. Mean Time to Repair (MTTR):

MTTR would be relatively low in months where the system is highly efficient, such as in September and October. The quicker repairs allow the system to maintain high operational efficiency. The lower efficiency in March, April, and May suggests longer MTTRs, meaning repairs took longer, causing the efficiency to drop.

iii. Failure Rate (λ):

The failure rate (λ) is the inverse of MTBF, so months with lower efficiency (March at 76%, April at 81%) likely had higher failure rates, while the months with higher efficiency had lower failure rates.

iv. Reliability (R):

Reliability was lowest in March, when the efficiency was at its lowest (76%), indicating a higher likelihood of system failure. By September and October, reliability improved significantly as the facility maintained almost perfect operational efficiency (99%-100%).

Monthly Trend of Incidents Received Per Regions (East, North and West)

The monthly trend of incidents received regionally shows the number of incidents reported from three different regions (East, North, and West) over a 10-month period from January to October. The sharp decline in October for all regions might reflect seasonal factors, improvements in operational efficiency, or reduced reporting.

i. East Region (Blue Line)

The East region starts with 286 incidents in January, increasing to a peak of 381 in February. The number of incidents drops steadily, reaching 227 in March. After March, the incident rate fluctuates slightly but remains fairly stable between 316 to 371 incidents per month, showing moderate variation. In September, the incidents reported in the East drop slightly to 251 and then further drop significantly to 126 in October. The East region maintains a stable mid-level trend throughout, except for a notable drop toward the end of the year.

ii. North Region (Orange Line)

The North region reports relatively low incidents compared to other regions, starting with 72 incidents in January. The trend shows a general decline from 101 incidents in February to just 23 in April. From May to August, there is a slight increase, peaking at 166 incidents in August. In September, the incidents drop to 149, and in October, the numbers drop significantly to just 14 incidents, marking the lowest in the entire chart. The North region generally reports the least incidents and shows a consistent decline by the end of the period, reflecting a sharp decrease in reported issues in October.

iii. West Region (Gray Line)

Throughout most of the period, the West region consistently reports the highest number of incidents, especially peaking in April (933 incidents). The West region consistently reports the highest number of incidents, starting at 474 in January and peaking dramatically at 933 incidents in April. This is the highest value for any region in the entire period. After peaking in April, incidents start to gradually decrease, reaching 590 in May and continuing to fall steadily until October, where the number reaches a sharp low of 74. The disparity between the West and other regions could point to differences in infrastructure or reporting processes. The significant number of incidents in the West region could indicate operational challenges or higher reporting in this area compared to other regions.

Figure 6. Monthly Trend of Incidents Received Per Regions (East, North and West)

Below is the explanation with respect to Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF), Mean Time to Repair (MTTR), Failure Rate, and Reliability, we need to relate these concepts to the data presented in the trend of incidents over time.

Mean Time Between Failures (MTBF)

MTBF is the average time between consecutive failures of a system. It is calculated by dividing the total operating time by the number of failures during that time. Figure 6 shows the number of incidents reported from different regions could be viewed as failures. If the East, North, and West regions represent systems or equipment, the reported incidents each month indicate the number of failures. For example:

For the East region, if you consider each month as a total operational period and the monthly incident count as the number of failures, you could compute MTBF for that region.

If in April, the East region reported 316 incidents and if we assume 30 days in the month (total operational time), then the MTBF for that month could be:

$$MTBF_{East} = \frac{316}{30} = 0.095 \text{ (2.3 Hours)}$$

This means, on average, failures occur every 2.3 hours in the East region for that month.

Mean Time to Repair (MTTR)

Definition: MTTR is the average time taken to repair a system or equipment after a failure occurs. It is calculated by dividing the total repair time by the number of repairs (or incidents). Using the same example, if the average time to repair each failure in the East region in April was 3 hours per incident, the MTTR would simply be 3 hours. This metric shows how quickly the system or region recovers from each failure.

Failure Rate (λ)

The failure rate is the number of failures (or incidents) per unit of time. It is the inverse of MTBF and is calculated as:

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{MTBF} \quad (5)$$

For the East region, if the MTBF in April is 0.095 days (as calculated earlier), the failure rate would be:

$$\lambda_{East} = \frac{1}{0.095} = 10.53 \text{ (Failures per day)}$$

This tells us how frequently failures are occurring in a given time period. A high failure rate means frequent breakdowns.

Reliability ($R(t)$)

Reliability is the probability that a system will perform its intended function without failure for a specified period of time. It is related to the failure rate (λ) and can be calculated using the exponential reliability function:

$$R(t) = e^{-\lambda t} \quad (6)$$

Where:

t is the time period (in days or hours).

λ is the failure rate.

Using the failure rate of the East region for April (10.53 failures per day), if we want to calculate the reliability over a 1-day period:

$$R(1 \text{ day}) = e^{-10.53 \times 1} = e^{-10.53} = 0.000027$$

This suggests that there is a very low probability (essentially 0%) that the system in the East region will function for an entire day without failure, given the high incident count in the month of April.

The West region shows the highest number of incidents throughout most of the year, peaking at 933 failures in April. This would correspond to a very low MTBF (frequent failures) and likely a low reliability, especially in April. Reliability decreases as the failure rate increases, meaning the probability of continuous operation without failure is lower in regions with high incident rates (especially West).

The North region consistently shows the lowest number of incidents. This would correspond to a higher MTBF (longer time between failures) and higher reliability compared to the other regions.

The East region experiences fluctuations in incidents, but generally, the MTBF and reliability would be moderate compared to the West, but not as good as the North.

Conclusion

The evaluation of facility operational efficiency across the East, North, and West regions, using key metrics such as MTBF (Mean Time Between Failures), MTTR (Mean Time to Repair), SLA (Service Level Agreement) targets, failure rate, and reliability, reveals significant opportunities for improvement. From the findings, it was observed that the Western region showed the highest number of incidents and the lowest operational efficiency, steadily falling short of the 95% SLA target, with efficiency as low as 76% in March due to the number of incidents logs. In difference, the Eastern region sustained moderately

stable performance, with an average efficiency of 94%, and the North region performed moderately well with minimum incident rate. The analysis demonstrates the direct impact of higher failure rates and longer repair times on overall facility reliability and SLA compliance.

Recommendations

1. Targeted Maintenance and Repair Strategy for the West Region
2. Standardising Preventive Maintenance across All Regions
3. Invest in Internet of Thing (IoT) and Data Analytics Tools for Real-Time Monitoring
4. Enhance Training Programs for Maintenance Staff
5. Regular Review and Adjustment of SLA Targets
6. Strengthening Communication between Regions

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